

Resilience and Self-Efficacy: A Correlational Study of 10th Grade Chemistry Students in Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 03, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Resilience, Self-Efficacy, Chemistry, Correlation, Secondary School.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4912254</p>	<p><i>This study was aimed to investigate the relationship between resilience and self-efficacy and to find the effect of resilience on self-efficacy in 10th-grade chemistry students. It was also aimed to identify the difference in resilience and self-efficacy by gender and academic stream. This quantitative, non-experimental, and correlational research emphasized the positivist paradigm with 200 chemistry students (10th grade) of district Lahore, Punjab-Pakistan on the basis of multi-stage sampling technique. The data were collected from individuals using the (Connor & Davidson, 2003) scale for resilience and (Sherer et al., 1982) scale for self efficacy. In addition, the researcher ensured the ethical considerations; and applied the independent sample t-test, linear regression, and Pearson correlation on the individuals' data. Resilience had a strong positive and significant relationship with self-efficacy; the results also indicated the strong significant effect of resilience on students' self-efficacy. This study will be supportive and helpful for teachers, principals, headteachers, parents and other stakeholders of the social setup. It will provide awareness about resilience and self-efficacy in context of chemistry learning which enhances springing back ability, problem-solving approach, self-confidence, self-awareness, cognitive approach, intellectual level, attentiveness, and attention for students and other stakeholders. In addition, it will minimize the coordination gap among students, teachers, headteachers, and parents. As un-buckled in the literature, few studies on these entitled constructs, especially resilience, impart a massive role in problem-solving in different contexts like resilience and self-efficacy. It is a very smoldering issue in the Pakistani context because only a few researchers try to discuss the construct of resilience concerning self-efficacy. Despite all, this research study opens new horizons for the new researcher on the same constructs at elementary, primary, higher secondary, and higher education levels in the different contexts of public/ private and locale.</i></p>

Introduction

Man is always searching for inventions and discoveries; his restless nature always inspires and compels him/her to think more and more about the overcoming of curiosity. In this perspective, they question themselves that what is a function of things? What is the reality behind the things? How we overcome the issues, problems and dilemmas? How confidence level developed in the personals (Emmert-Streib et al., 2020; Green, 2016).

The conception of self efficacy is old, introduced by Bundura in 1977 (Elgendi et al., 2021; Maciejewski et al., 2000) that was derived from his book published on social work in 1963 (Bandura & Walters, 1963) but the concept of resilience is introduced in education recently; and is taken from psychology and sociology (Mirza & Arif, 2018; Van Bavel et al., 2020; Woodroof, 1990). Primarily, the concept of resilience was used in industry and project management; in education, the scientific study regarding resilience in children was made in the 1960s (Masten & Reed, 2002; PeConga et al., 2020; Tusaie & Dyer, 2004; Vernon, 2004). Therefore, this research work is formulated to find the relationship between resilience and self-efficacy of 10th- grade chemistry students in district Lahore, Pakistan.

The Rationale of the Study

Science, especially chemistry, imparts an effect on students' learning in chemistry at the 10th-grade level. Resilience as well as self-efficacy are essential variables which enable the students to overcome and springs back the learning problems. The self-efficacy is; "belief of a person in his or her ability to organize and execute certain behaviors that are necessary to produce given attainments" (Bandura, 1986; Salim, 1997) and resilience is stated as capacity to "sustain psychological stability in the face of stress" (Herrman et al., 2011). Students must spring back to solve the problems which they face during the learning process. After overcoming the problems and issues during the learning process, students become more confident and make good decisions. As chemistry is considered a very tough and dry subject and not easy to understand; so, resilient nature of students are required for better understanding which caused to enhance the self efficacy.

Research Gap

Science is considered a broader term comprised of different subjects like Chemistry, Mathematics, Physics, Computer science, and biology. The teaching of science is compulsory at the primary and elementary levels in Pakistan. Still, in the 9th-grade, students have to choose the different academic streams like biology, and chemistry (Dildar et al., 2016; Iqbal et al., 2009; Khushik & Diemer, 2018). Different pedagogical skills are used to teach chemistry in versatile ways. Resilience as well as self-efficacy are exceptional variables those are measurable. In Chemistry, the confidence level, like self-efficacy of teachers and teachers, varies from person to person and place to place depending on the environmental grounds and condition (Cassidy, 2015). Secondary level teachers exercise concealed capabilities and unbuckled the information and unlock knowledge for better learning and constructive achievement in chemistry. It is a tremendous challenge for the chemistry teacher to blow up the students' resilience, self-efficacy, and academic achievement by applying various teaching methods during chemistry teaching. In this critical situation of COVID-19, it is a need for time to demonstrate a clear view of current situations in the context of resilience and self-efficacy (Austin & Gregory, 2021; Benight & Cieslak, 2011; Giovannini et al., 2020; Walsh, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

The idea of resilience is new in education (Mirza & Arif, 2018); it keeps a unique space in education, especially in the pandemic condition of COVID-19. The 10th-grade chemistry students face number of problems during the learning process, especially in Pakistan, as; chemistry is considered a complex subject (Iqbal et al., 2009). So, it is the need of time to identify the problem and its solution. In this context, it is necessary to find how the students got confidence (self-efficacy), overcome the learning problems, and spring back (resilience) to solve the problems in chemistry. It is evident, learning problems mainly capacity to recover quickly from difficulties and then confidence level. So, it means that it is the relationship between spring back, i.e., resilience, and confidence level, i.e., self-efficacy.

Research Objectives

The researcher framed the objectives as:

1. To investigate the relationship between resilience and self-efficacy of 10th-grade chemistry students.
2. To compare the difference in resilience and self-efficacy of 10th-grade chemistry students by academic stream and gender.
3. To examine the effect of resilience on self-efficacy of 10th-grade chemistry students.

Conceptual Framework

This study was aimed to identify the relationship between resilience and self-efficacy of 10th-grade chemistry students in Lahore, Pakistan. The researcher is also trying to find the effect of resilience on the self-efficacy of 10th-grade chemistry students in Lahore, Pakistan if a robust positive correlation was formed between the unbuckled variables. The resilience had a positive relationship with self-efficacy (Flach, 1988; Hamill, 2003; Martin & Marsh, 2009). The resilience has a association with self-efficacy (Hamad, 2020; Hudson, 2007). A positive correlation was explored between resilience and self-efficacy (Speight, 2009). Self-efficacy, resilience, and religiosity possess a positive correlation (Ganaprakasam et al., 2020). Resilience positively correlates with self-efficacy (Fayazi & Bagherian, 2018; Li et al., 2018). According to Sagone et al. (2020), resilience was

moderately positively correlated with self-efficacy. A research study was conducted on nursing students with findings that resilience has a strong and positive correlation with self-efficacy (Moon et al., 2015).

Literature Review

In this research study, the researcher was tried to find the relationship between resilience and self-efficacy of 10th-grade chemistry students. This research study will also be helpful to the teachers and beginner researchers. The major concern of the researcher was how to make the connection of resilience with self-efficacy in the context of chemistry at 10th-grade. Various techniques were used to overcome the problems and issues of the students during the learning process, but resilience plays a vital role in overcoming the issues and problems (Keye & Pidgeon, 2013; Lakhan et al.; Tsibidaki, 2021).

Resilience is a capacity to overcome or spend aimed life after passing through the problems and issues (Calhoun & Tedeschi, 2004; Lakhan et al., 2020; Naidu, 2021; Robertson, 2021). Resilience has an important place in education and research after failed attempts in the context of the teaching-learning process (Hayward et al., 2010; Tsibidaki, 2021; Weidlich & Kalz, 2021). Resilient support the situation under the challenging condition (Branzei & Abdelnour, 2010; Rachmawati et al., 2021; Sagone et al., 2020). This research study was enhanced to inspect the value and significance of resilience on personal attention to commence the teaching-learning situation in an unpleasant situation. The aim to take the first step is extensively used in the intellectual construct (Djourouva et al., 2020; Hassanein et al., 2021; Thompson, 2009). Intentions have a significant influence on manufacturing behavior like self-employment and starting a new business. (Fishbein et al., 1980; MacRae, 2021; Orkaizagirre-Gómara et al., 2020), The intention is the first ray of light in a classically continuing progression of starting the innovative trend (Morgan & Krueger, 1993; Ngui & Lay, 2020).

A wide-ranging literature review unbuckled that self-efficacy and resilience are interconnected (Yada et al., 2021), which affect initiatives under hazardous situations (Renko et al., 2021). But, social cognitive theory guides the prior research studies to connect self-efficacy with resilience (Benight & Bandura, 2004; Linley et al., 2004; Santoro et al., 2020) and intentions (Jia et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2005). Yet, the research indicates that three valuable constructs; self-efficacy, resilience, and intentions are missing (Renko et al., 2021). In the current research study, this gap can be fulfilled by providing two precise assistances to theory.

Self-efficacy does not identify the intentions in a hazardous situation (Samuels et al., 2010; Wen et al., 2020). In the context of “social cognitive theory”, the idea of adverse attitude, individual factors, and ecological pressure are working interactively (Bandura, 2010; Liu et al., 2020; Sabouripour et al., 2021). In a hazardous situation, self-efficacy relies on personal effects discussed in the farmer research studies like resilience (Odede, 2021). A dangerous situation is also a critical feature that influences the intentions during perceptions of risk (Aker, 2021). Resilience is the central fact to understand the concept of resistance against the failure (Calhoun & Tedeschi, 2004; Folkman & Moskowitz, 2000; Kim, 2020). In this context, understanding is very significant for the various government and private educational institutions. Training programs play an essential role in developing countries because they are in the initial design phase (Khan et al., 2020; Tsibidaki, 2021).

Resilience is constructive and positively connected to starting the work in any critical situation (Shah et al., 2020; Tedeschi et al., 2007). The persons with more resilience are not much affected by the pre-determined and supposed danger (Yeung & Li, 2021); they easily overcome the issue and problems and start the work quickly (Bullough et al., 2014; Naidu, 2021). Resilience is a state in which a person reacts to mobilize in time to eradicate the stress (Balua, 2021; Morales-Rodríguez, 2021; Torres, 2010). On the other hand, when problems and issues are near to resilient, they are in an excellent position to handle the perilous situation; they are nearly taking action in unavoidable conditions (Balua, 2021; Calhoun et al., 2010; Folkman & Moskowitz, 2007).

Terrifying and mystifying are fundamental challenges for the students and teachers (Balua, 2021), and they are expected to be minimized with positive and constructive outcomes (Hamadeh Kerbage et al., 2021; Tedeschi et al., 2015). Resilience is the leading cause of such positive and constructive outcomes during unexpected and unpleasant situations (Nečasová, 2021; Westphal & Bonanno, 2007). Resilience has such capacity

to overcome the adverse situation in a better way by participating in intentions to start and grow a business (Krueger, 2008; Lambert & Corpus, 2021). High resilience and adverse consequence of danger are inversely proportional in the context of attention and intentions (Praetorius et al., 2021).

Methodology

The deductive method was used to find the relationship between the entitled variable (Meza et al., 2018). This quantitative and non-experimental study trends the positivist paradigm, providing clear-cut and concrete guidelines regarding the variables (Kumatongo & Muzata, 2021; Phillips et al., 2000). The researcher adopted the correlational research design to find the relationship between the variables.

Population of the Study

The term population is the total number of the elements present in the group from which required individuals are selected (Hutchings, 2021; Wallen & Fraenkel, 2013). The chemistry students of the district Lahore, including male and female, were the study population studying in 10th-grade. There are five Tehsils of Lahore; City, Cantt., Model Town, Raiwind, Shalimar, and Nishter. Therefore, the researcher delimited his study to Tehsil City only. There are 273 schools in Lahore city in which 21,439 students are studied (Shah, 2018).

Sample of the Study

Sample were selected subjects/individuals representing the whole population (Charles, 1998; Lodico et al., 2010). According to Rahman (2020), the sample supports the researcher for the convenience of the generalization of the results. A technique of multi-stage sampling was adapted to the select the sample. Based on the environmental condition, especially in critical condition of COVID-19, only 200 students were selected as sample. It is further categorized into 100 males and 100 females based on gender. Moreover, based on the academic stream, 50 males of computer science and 50 of biology were selected; similarly, 50 females of computer science and 50 female from biology were also selected. So the total sample were 200 students. Diagrammatical representation is as:

Instruments

The researcher used two adapted instruments for data collection. One adapted questionnaire in the context of resilience scale (Connor & Davidson, 2003) possessing the 25-items with 5-indicators like personal competence, confidence, positive acceptance, control and spirituality with Cronbach Alpha value of .929; and second is self-efficacy scale (Sherer et al., 1982) owing 40-items with 5-indicators like self confidence, students' initiative, , success and failure, social attraction, and social attention with Cronbach Alpha value of .884. These were the major tools for data collection of the individuals. Google form was used to collect the data from the subjects.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1. *Relationship of Resilience and Students' self-efficacy*

Variables	<i>N</i>	<i>r</i> -value	<i>Sig.</i>
Resilience & Self-efficacy	200	.810**	.001

** $p < .001$ (2-tailed)

The table 1 depicts the relationship between resilience and students' self-efficacy by using Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It was concluded that resilience had a significant strong positive relationship with students' self-efficacy, ($r = .810^{**}$, $n = 200$, $p < .001$).

Table 2. *Relationship of Resilience Factors with Students' Self-efficacy*

Sub-scales of Resilience and Self-efficacy	1	2	3	4	5	6
Personal Competence	1	.733**	.535**	.530**	.702**	.712**
Confidence		1	.490**	.574**	.720**	.756**
Positive Acceptance			1	.555**	.647**	.566**
Control				1	.594**	.562**
Spirituality					1	.771**
Self-efficacy						1

** $p < .001$ (2-tailed), $n = 200$

Table 2 indicated that the correlation between resilience and students' self-efficacy. The factors of resilience such as: Personal Competence ($r = .712^{**}$, $p < .001$), Confidence ($r = .756^{**}$, $p < .001$), Positive Acceptance ($r = .566^{**}$, $p < .001$), Control ($r = .562^{**}$, $p < .001$), and Spirituality ($r = .771^{**}$, $p < .001$) were having positive significant relationship with students' self-efficacy. It was concluded that the dimensions of resilience had positive and significant correlation with students' self-efficacy.

Table 3. *Differences in Resilience and Students' Self-efficacy with Regard to their Gender*

Variables	Gender	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
Resilience	Male	100	104.56	11.88	3.698	198	.090
	Female	100	97.83	13.82			
Self-efficacy	Male	100	171.38	17.93	2.286	183	.004
	Female	100	164.56	23.86			

Table 3 indicated that an "independent sample t-test" was run for the comparison mean scores of resilience and students' self-efficacy concerning their gender. It was concluded that students' self-efficacy had a significant difference at $p = .05$.

Table 4. *Independent sample t-test on Different Sub-scales of Resilience and Students' Self-efficacy in Terms of their Gender*

Sub-scales of Resilience and Self-efficacy	Gender	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
Personal Competence	Male	100	21.88	2.77	2.995	183	.000
	Female	100	20.50	3.68			
Confidence	Male	100	21.62	2.62	2.513	191	.037
	Female	100	20.59	3.16			
Positive Acceptance	Male	100	19.65	3.29	3.404	198	.331
	Female	100	18.09	3.19			
Control	Male	100	20.15	3.26	3.062	198	.938
	Female	100	18.75	3.21			
Spirituality	Male	100	21.26	2.43	3.114	172	.000
	Female	100	19.90	3.63			

Student Initiative	Male	100	33.74	4.57	1.190	187	.001
	Female	100	32.86	5.81			
Social Attention	Male	100	34.00	3.97	2.301	190	.059
	Female	100	32.55	4.89			
Success/Failure	Male	100	34.57	3.74	2.598	180	.000
	Female	100	32.91	5.182			
Social Attraction	Male	100	34.31	4.39	1.611	190	.035
	Female	100	33.19	5.39			
Self-confidence	Male	100	34.76	4.34	2.523	191	.008
	Female	100	33.05	5.21			

Table 4 revealed that an “independent sample t-test” was run for the comparison of mean scores of resilience and students’ self-efficacy concerning their gender. It was concluded that only three sub-variables of resilience, such as personal competence, confidence and spirituality, had a significant difference out of five factors. The results also indicated that four self-efficacy factors such as student initiative, success/failure, social interaction and self-confidence out of five factors had a significant difference based on their gender at $p.05$.

Table 5. *Differences in Resilience and Students’ Self-efficacy with Regard to their Academic Stream*

Variables	Academic Stream	N	M	SD	t	df	p
Resilience	Computer	100	102.06	14.74	.921	187	.012
	Biology	100	100.33	11.63			
Self-Efficacy	Computer	100	165.97	23.18	-1.329	191	.022
	Biology	100	169.97	19.18			

Table 5 illustrated that an “independent sample t-test” was run for comparison mean scores of resilience and students’ self-efficacy concerning their gender. It was concluded that resilience and students’ self-efficacy had a significant difference at $p = .05$.

Table 6. *Difference on Different Sub-scales of Resilience and Students’ Self-efficacy by Academic Stream*

Sub-scales of Resilience and Self-efficacy	Academic Stream	N	M	SD	t	df	p
Personal Competence	Computer	100	21.21	3.45	.085	198	.347
	Biology	100	21.17	3.21			
Confidence	Computer	100	21.13	3.16	.120	198	.231
	Biology	100	21.08	2.71			
Positive Acceptance	Computer	100	19.26	3.78	1.666	181	.000
	Biology	100	18.48	2.76			
Control	Computer	100	20.01	3.35	2.429	198	.588
	Biology	100	18.89	3.17			
Spirituality	Computer	100	20.45	3.22	-.582	198	.454
	Biology	100	20.71	3.11			
Student Initiative	Computer	100	32.93	5.34	1.000	198	.533
	Biology	100	33.67	5.13			
Social Attention	Computer	100	33.13	4.86	-.454	198	.082
	Biology	100	33.42	4.13			
Success/Failure	Computer	100	33.40	4.62	1.050	198	.810
	Biology	100	34.08	4.55			
Social Attraction	Computer	100	33.17	5.46	1.670	187	.011
	Biology	100	34.33	4.29			
Self-confidence	Computer	100	33.34	5.53	1.652	181	.002
	Biology	100	34.47	4.04			

Table 6 revealed that an “independent sample t-test” was run to compare mean scores of resilience and students’ self-efficacy concerning their academic stream. It was concluded that only one sub-variable of resilience, such as

positive acceptance, had a significant difference out of five factors. The results also reported that only two self-efficacy factors, such as Social Attraction and self-confidence, out of five factors had a significant difference based on their academic stream at $p.05$.

Table 7. *Effect of resilience on Self-efficacy*

Variables	<i>B</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>Model R Square</i>
Resilience and Self-efficacy	.810	19.452	.001	.656

Table 7 illustrated that linear regression results, the R^2 value (0.656) explained the variance in the criterion due to the predictor. So, the variance in students' self-efficacy is (65.6%) due to resilience. The beta value (0.810) is significant with $p = .001$. The results indicated the strong significant effect of resilience on students' self-efficacy with β value 0.810 at $p = .001$.

Discussion

Resilience is a unique trait of an individual purely based on environmental conditions and environmental ground (Ahmed et al., 2019) and highlights the particular to overcome and rebound (Verdolini et al., 2021). This study explain that resilience had a strong and positive significant relationship with students' self-efficacy that support the results of (Flach, 1988; Hamill, 2003; Martin & Marsh, 2009) whose findings were; a resilience has positive correlation with self-efficacy. Similarly, the current results support the study of (Hamad, 2020; Hudson, 2007), whose findings were; A resilience is significantly correlated with self-efficacy. In the same context, this study supportes findings of (Speight, 2009) that a resilience is positively correlated with self-efficacy. In the same way, the results of this study also support the findings of (Ganaprakasam et al., 2020) conducted in Malaysia as; self-efficacy, resilience and religiosity possess a positive correlation.

Similarly, the results of this research also aligned with the findings of (Fayazi & Bagherian, 2018; Li et al., 2018) that resilience has a positive correlation with self-efficacy. The current results of the study also aligned with the study by Sagone et al. (2020) in Italy and find out that resilience and self efficacy were had moderate-positive relationship. A research study was conducted in Korea on nursing students with findings that resilience has a strong and positive correlation with self-efficacy (Moon et al., 2015); the current study results also support this study.

In addition to correlation, t-test and regression were also applied, which enhances the research beauty of this study. In the context of resilience, male and female students have no difference in resilience, but in self-efficacy, male students have more self-efficacy than female. Similarly, in resilience, computer students are more resilient than biology students, but biology students have more self-efficacy than computer students in self-efficacy. The regression analysis results show the strong significant effect of resilience on self-efficacy as variance in self-efficacy is (65.6%).

Conclusion

This structured study aimed to find the association of resilience with self-efficacy. Based on the finding, various conclusions were made after the data analysis. It is concluded that resilience has a positive association and relationship with self-efficacy. The resilience factors such as personal competence, confidence, positive acceptance, and spirituality have a positively significant positive relationship with self-efficacy. In resilience regarding gender, both male and female students have insignificant differences in resilience; no difference exists between them. In self-efficacy regarding gender, male and female students have a mean difference as males have more self-efficacy than females. "Independent sample t-test" was applied on the factors regarding self-efficacy and resilience and concluded that in personal competence factor of resilience, male and female have mean difference as male have more personal competence than female. In the confidence that is also a factor of resilience, a mean difference exists between males and females as males are more confident than females in resilience. The positive acceptance, which is the 3rd factor of resilience, an insignificant difference exists between

male and female means both male and female same level of positive acceptance in the context of resilience. Control is the 4th factor of resilience; an insignificant difference exists between male and female, it means the male and female having same level of control in the context of resilience. The 5th factor of resilience is spirituality; results show the significant difference between the mean score, as male students possess more spirituality than females. In the case of self-efficacy, five (5) factors are discussed by gender. The first factor is students' initiative; this factor means that score difference existed as males are better than females. The 2nd factor is social attention; in this factor, a non-significant difference existed as male and female students have the same social attention concerning self-efficacy. The 3rd factor is success/failure; a significant difference exists in male and female. The 4th factor is social attraction; in this factor, male students are much better than female students. The 5th factor is social confidence; in this factor, male students have more social confidence than female students.

Similarly, resilience factors and self-efficacy were interpreted based on academic streams (biology and computer science). In resilience, the factors like personal competence, confidence, control and spirituality both have insignificant difference as both biology and computer students have no difference towards these factors, but in positive acceptance, a significant difference exists between computer and biology students; as biology students have more trends towards positive acceptance than computer students. In self-efficacy, the factors like student initiative, social attention, and success/failure have insignificant differences as both biology and computer students were having the same trends towards these factors. Still, factors like social attraction and self-confidence have a mean difference as biology students have more trends than computer students. It is pronounced from the results that variance in self-efficacy is (65.6%) due to resilience; the results were also indicated the strong significant effect of resilience on self-efficacy with β value 0.810 at $p=.01$

Limitations and Future Research Concerns

Everything has its advantages, disadvantages and limitations. In this study, the researcher collected the data from individuals/ subjects on the basis of multi-stage random sampling technique due to the critical and pandemic condition of COVID-19. The data were collected from male and female individuals of district Lahore, Tehsil city only, from public sectors schools. Adopted tools were used for this purpose. The future researcher can use the different sampling techniques to select individuals like simple random, stratified sampling, etc., in their research studies. As research is a broader field, the researcher can also select the private male and female schools from other Tehsils of Lahore; other districts of Punjab-Pakistan can also be used for research. This research study is conducted at the secondary level and sets the trend for the future researcher, so the future researcher may also research primary, elementary and higher school levels. Self-structured questionnaires may also be used by finding their reliability as well as validity. Other quantitative (like experimental research, etc.), qualitative and mixed-method studies may be used for future research using the same variables.

Acknowledgment

The authors are deeply thankful to almighty ALLAH SUBHANA WA TALA (سبحان و تعالی) and NABI AKRAM (خاتم النبیین ﷺ) for completion of this research work/manuscript. The researchers are also thankful to parents, honorable teachers and friends for helping hands and prayers to complete this manuscript.

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